

Cognitive and Geographical Proximities Across Universities: Evidence from the OpenAlex Database

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Abstract

We analyzed scientific collaboration networks using the OpenAlex database via BigQuery. By establishing a threshold of a minimum of 60,000 works, we identified 473 distinct universities worldwide. The impact of geographical proximity on scientific collaboration was measured in kilometers. For cognitive proximity, we utilized a new classification recently proposed by researchers from Leiden University. To examine the relationship between cognitive and geographical proximity among universities, we applied the gravity model of spatial interaction along with count data models. The results indicated an average reduction of 10.27% in collaboration for every 1,000 kilometers of distance between two universities.

1. Introduction

There is a significant debate regarding the influence of geographical proximity on the advancement of science and technology (S&T). Some researchers have noted that local knowledge flows are crucial for interactive learning (Gertler, 2003; Glaeser et al., 1992; Storper & Venables, 2004). However, the literature also emphasizes that geographical proximity alone is not a sufficient condition for promoting interactive learning and innovation, as physical distance itself cannot stimulate interaction among local actors (Boschma, 2005; Broekel, 2015).

Geographical proximity can be complemented by other non-spatial dimensions, such as cognitive proximity. This concept refers to the similarities in how individuals interpret and evaluate new knowledge. Actors who share the same knowledge are more capable of learning from one another (Boschma, 2005). In this context, universities play a crucial role, as they are essential to the modern capitalist system, integrating the institutional structures that support S&T activities (Nelson, 1990).

Van Eck and Waltman (2024) have recently proposed a classification system for research publications based on the Leiden algorithm. We utilize this new classification to calculate cognitive proximity. Our objective is to identify the extent to which different types of proximity influence university interactions. The novelty of our approach lies in how we leverage both geographical and cognitive proximities through the OpenAlex database. In this context, it is essential to analytically isolate the effect of geographical proximity from other dimensions of proximity, with a particular emphasis on cognitive aspects. This will be

explained in detail in the empirical strategy, which employs the gravity model of spatial interaction and count data models.

The contribution of this study is to provide new empirical evidence regarding the relationship between different types of proximity, which has significant implications for S&T policies. This research will address the following question: Does geographical proximity continue to play a significant role among universities? In addition to this introduction, the study is organized into five sections. The second section presents the theoretical framework. The third section outlines the materials and methods, which are further divided into data description and empirical modeling. The fourth section discusses the results, while the fifth section encompasses the discussion and conclusion of the study.

2. Theoretical Basis

According to Boschma (2005), geographical proximity offers advantages by facilitating interorganizational learning; however, it is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition for such learning to occur. Consequently, there is a pressing need for empirical research on this topic, particularly since cognitive proximity may be viewed as a prerequisite for effective learning. Garcia et al. (2018) discovered that cognitive proximity significantly influences the geographical distance of collaborations between firms and universities. Specifically, research groups and collaborating firms with high cognitive proximity are able to work together across greater geographical distances. This extensive body of literature underscores that learning and knowledge creation are often cumulative processes that are essential for achieving a competitive advantage across regions.

The ability to assimilate new knowledge is influenced by cognitive proximity. This means that the cognitive foundation must be appropriately aligned with the new knowledge to facilitate effective communication. Furthermore, geographical proximity appears to be sufficient for interactive learning to occur when combined with a certain level of cognitive proximity. On one hand, excessive cognitive distance can lead to communication challenges. On the other hand, insufficient cognitive distance may result in a lack of novel ideas, as noted by Nooteboom (2000) and Boschma (2005). Some empirical studies indicate that geographical proximity is particularly important in promoting interdisciplinary research collaborations, which typically involve low cognitive proximity. In contrast, individuals working within the same field of expertise (high cognitive proximity) tend to collaborate over greater geographical distances on average, as discussed by Boschma and Frenken (2009) in their comprehensive literature review.

Scientific collaboration networks can be analyzed using spatial effects (Scherngell & Hu, 2011) and computational graphs, where researchers are represented as nodes and co-authorships as edges (Chen et al., 2019). These graphs can be represented by an adjacency matrix, with the nodes of the network arranged in rows and columns, forming an $n \times n$ structure. Scientific collaboration networks are undirected graphs with weighted edges that indicate the intensity of collaborations among researchers (Newman, 2001). Additionally, the aggregation of geographical units is common in spatial scientometrics (Boschma & Frenken, 2009; Hoekman et al., 2010; Scherngell & Hu, 2011; Sidone et al., 2016). In this study, we adopted the full-counting method, assigning one unit of collaboration to each institution or region based on their participation in scientific publications. We adjusted our data to align with the specifications of the data model. Ultimately, we employed count data models to estimate the effects of geographical and cognitive proximities on the probability of scientific

collaboration. When associating a university with a geographical unit, the adjacency matrix is composed of the total interuniversity collaborations within geographical units i and j .

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Data description

Waltman and Van Eck (2024) employed the extended direct citation approach associated with the Leiden algorithm. Their classification encompasses 71 million journal articles, conference papers, preprints, and book chapters in the OpenAlex database, published between 2000 and 2023, which are interconnected through citation links. Utilizing 1.715 billion citation links, they constructed a three-level hierarchical classification. Each publication was assigned to a research area at each of the three classification levels. Research areas consist of publications that are relatively strongly connected by citation links and are therefore expected to be topically related. Additionally, they developed a classification comprising 4,521 research areas at the most granular level, 917 research areas at the intermediate level, and 20 research areas at the least granular level. The classification of works based on clusters formed by bibliographic coupling is available at (<https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/an-open-approach-for-classifying-research-publications>), with the dataset accessible at (<https://zenodo.org/records/10560276>). The tables containing the clusters at macro, meso, and micro levels have also been uploaded to the same environment as a new dataset. This allows for the collection of additional metadata associated with the institutions i and j .

In this study, we utilized the least granular level, known as macro clusters, to calculate cognitive proximity among universities. Data were collected from a cloud-stored version of the OpenAlex full data dump. This version is organized into tables, as demonstrated in the code available at (<https://github.com/insyspo/openalex>), for integration into the Google BigQuery platform. The assembled tables can be queried for pertinent information, including latitude, longitude, country codes, number of works, and number of authors.

OpenAlex is a freely accessible knowledge graph that includes cited reference data as one of its connections among publications and researchers, containing metadata for approximately 250 million scholarly works (Priem et al., 2022). The data is licensed under CC0 and is openly available through an API, enabling users to analyze it effectively. Each work is identified by an internal identifier known as the OpenAlex ID, which is used to link it to other works. Each work has an attribute called in its metadata, which consists of a list of OpenAlex IDs that identify its references. The primary method for querying data from OpenAlex is through its API. Each entity type (works, authors, institutions, sources, publishers, concepts) has its own endpoint, which can be accessed using a variety of filters to specify a desired subset.

We have defined the largest institutions as those with more than 60,000 works indexed in OpenAlex. This threshold represents our initial effort to analyze a substantial number of interactions within OpenAlex. For each of these institutions, we have collected the macro cluster identifications for all the works. We match works and institutions based on authorship (https://github.com/alyssonmazoni/institutions_cognitive). We consider multiple affiliations, and some data for certain institutions in OpenAlex have been cleaned.

We transformed the table of works and their corresponding clusters for the selected institutions into a new format, where each row represents an institution and each column

corresponds to a cluster number. This was accomplished by pivoting the table for the clusters and aggregating the works by institution. By normalizing the number of works in each cluster for every institution against the total number of works within that institution, we obtain a vector representation of the research effort related to the area classification for each institution.

Two institutions can be compared based on the similarity of their cognitive efforts if their vectors are closely aligned. To achieve this, we utilize the scalar product (cosine) of the two vectors representing the institutions. A resulting value of 1 indicates perfectly aligned institutions, while a value of 0 signifies institutions that operate in completely disjoint areas. By leveraging the distance and collaboration metadata available in OpenAlex, we can calculate geographical distance (based on latitude and longitude) and collaboration distance, which is defined as the number of works with shared authorship between two institutions. All these processes were automated using Python and BigQuery. Additionally, we employed Google Colab, which facilitates the integration of BigQuery with the Python programming language.

3.2. Empirical model

Statistical regressions enable the use of scientific collaborations as the dependent variable and dimensions of proximity as independent variables, based on the gravity model of spatial interaction (Hoekman et al., 2010; Ponds et al., 2007). Spatial interaction models describe functions that characterize the origin i and destination j of interactions, as well as the separation between two regions, $i \in j$. The general regression model is represented by the following equation:

$$Y_{ij} = X_{ij} + \varepsilon_{ij}; \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

Y_{ij} is a stochastic dependent variable that corresponds to the observed scientific collaboration between two regions i and j ($y_{ij} \geq 0$). X_{ij} is a function that captures the stochastic relationship to other random variables. ε_{ij} is the error term that varies across inter-regional pairs, $i \in j$. X_{ij} is specified as a function of covariates and corresponds to the general gravity model. Our objective is to measure the relative importance of two regions (the origin and destination) and the distance in determining the scientific collaborations.

$$X_{ij} = O_i D_j S(u_{ij}); \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

The functions O_i e D_j characterize the interactions of regions origin i and destination j , which can be described by *power functions* in consonance with classical spatial interaction theory (Sen & Smith, 1995). The specification of the spatial separation term occurs in the form of a multivariate exponential function, enabling the inclusion of other dimensions of proximity in the model simultaneously. Therefore, the functions take the following forms:

$$O_i = O(o_i, \alpha_1) = o_i^{\alpha_1}; \quad i = 1, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

$$D_j = D(d_j, \alpha_2) = d_j^{\alpha_2}; \quad j = 1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

$$S(u_{ij}) = S(u_{ij}, \beta) = \exp\left[\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k u_{ij}^{(k)}\right]; \quad i, j=1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

The variables o_i and d_j measurement characteristics of regions i and j , and the variable $u_{ij}^{(k)}$ represents k measures of spatial separation between regions i and j . The terms α_1 e α_2 are parameters to be estimated in two specifications, while the β_k term refers to the set of k unknown parameters associated with each of the k measures on spatial separation between regions i and j . We considered the special case $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$ where the variables of origin and destination are symmetrical, and scientific interactions result from an undirected graph. We derived the following empirical model to be estimated by substituting equations from the initial model:

$$Y_{ij} = \alpha + o_i^{\alpha_1} d_j^{\alpha_2} \exp[\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k u_{ij}^{(k)}] + \varepsilon_{ij}; \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

The variables of origin (o_i) and destination (d_j) are measured by the total scientific publications in each institution. Interuniversity distances were calculated in kilometers (km) using the Geopy library in the Python programming language. It is assumed that collaborations among universities positively depend on total publications in each of them. As the number of publications in one region increase the probability of collaboration with other regions, the estimation of the mass terms tends to be statistically significant and close to unity ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$). We used two parameters for separation variables. The first one (β_1) consists of a matrix of geographical distance in which every element $u_{ij}^{(1)}$ is calculated by distance in km between two universities, i and j . The second parameter (β_2) was used to measure cognitive relationship across universities.

Count data models can be employed to address specification issues in spatial interaction models, particularly when a log-normal specification for model equation 6 is inappropriate (Long & Freese, 2001). This specification challenge can be mitigated by interpreting the model as a count data model, which assumes that the data-generating process yields only non-negative integers. The number of scientific collaborations may adhere to a Poisson distribution, as expressed in the following equation:

$$\Pr(Y_{ij} = y_{ij} \mid X_{ij}) = \frac{e^{-\mu_{ij}} \mu_{ij}^{y_{ij}}}{y_{ij}!}; \quad i, j = 1, \dots, n; \quad y_{ij} = 0, 1, 2, \dots \quad (7)$$

Where μ_{ij} is the set of independent variables in the empirical model (6):

$$\mu_{ij} = X_{ij} = \exp [\alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \log(o_i) + \alpha_2 \log(d_j) + [\sum_{k=1}^K \beta_k u_{ij}^{(k)}]] \quad (8)$$

One assumes that data are generated from a Poisson process, and the model can be consistently estimated using the standard maximum likelihood method if the property of equidispersion is confirmed by the observed data. In cases of overdispersion, standard errors are underestimated, which invalidates the hypothesis test (Cameron & Trivedi, 2013; Hilbe, 2011). The Negative Binomial distribution is a common alternative in empirical studies of scientific collaboration (Hoekman et al., 2010; Scherngell & Barber, 2011). It accounts for unobserved heterogeneity by introducing an additional parameter. The Negative Binomial density function (9) and the conditional variance (10) are given by the following equations:

$$\Pr (Y_{ij}= y_{ij} | X_{ij}) = \frac{\Gamma(y_{ij}+\alpha^{-1})}{y_{ij}! \Gamma(\alpha^{-1})} \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha^{-1}}{\alpha^{-1}+\mu_{ij}}\right)^{\alpha^{-1}} \cdot \left(\frac{\mu_{ij}}{\alpha^{-1}+\mu_{ij}}\right)^{y_{ij}} \quad (9)$$

$$V [Y_{ij}|X_{ij}] = \mu_{ij} + \alpha \mu_{ij}^2; \quad \mu_{ij} = E [Y_{ij}|X_{ij}] \quad (10)$$

Where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function, and α is the heterogeneity parameter.

4. Results

We identified universities in various regions around the world. By establishing a threshold of at least 60,000 scientific publications, we identified 473 distinct universities globally. This results in 473 nodes and 54,291 edges in the computational graphs (see Figure 1). Among the top ten universities for scientific collaboration worldwide, institutions are located in the United States, France, and China, including Johns Hopkins University, Sorbonne Université, and the Chinese Academy of Sciences.

The two institutions with the highest cognitive proximity—Brown University and Providence University—are situated less than 1 kilometer apart. In contrast, some pairs with the lowest cognitive proximities are separated by approximately 10,000 kilometers, such as North China Electric Power University and the University of Alabama at Birmingham. It is important to note that this relationship is not linear. For example, there are pairs of institutions with high cognitive proximity that are separated by more than 6,000 kilometers, such as Radboud University and the University of Pittsburgh.

Figure 1 illustrates the word map, with nodes ranked based on the intensity of their collaboration. Almost all nodes are interconnected; however, the relative strength of these connections is indicated by the size of the nodes. Additionally, it is clear that the Global South exhibits weaker connectivity.

Source: own elaboration on Gephi using the OpenAlex Database

Figure 1: Georeferencing graphs from various universities around the world

We found that the increasing physical distance between two universities decreases the probability of scientific collaboration, as indicated by the count data models presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Count data models for scientific collaborations

Model	Variables	Results
Poisson	Origin-destination ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$)	.9734689 *** (.0003904)
	Geographical Distance (β_1)	-.0001568 *** (7.50e-08)
	Cognitive Proximity (β_2)	1.859529 *** (.0017233)
	Constant	-17.91671 *** (.0069637)
	Pseudo R ²	0.5772
Negative Binomial	Origin-destination ($\alpha_1 = \alpha_2$)	.8776679 *** (.0082553)
	Geographical Distance (β_1)	-.0001084 *** (7.71e-07)
	Cognitive Proximity (β_2)	2.151012 *** (.019856)
	Constant	-18.00866 *** (.1325997)
	Heterogeneity (α)	.8975536 *** (.0049737)
	Pseudo R ²	0.0731

Note: n=54,291. Parentheses indicate standard errors; *** corresponds to statistical significance levels of 0.001.

All results were statistically significant. The parameter for geographical proximity was negative in both the Poisson and Negative Binomial models, suggesting that increased collaboration is associated with shorter geographical distances. Conversely, the parameter for cognitive proximity was positive in both models, indicating that greater scientific collaboration correlates with increased cognitive proximity. The estimates of mass terms (origin and destination) were statistically significant and close to unit, demonstrating the adequate specification of these models. The Negative Binomial model performed better overall, as it captured the heterogeneity with a parameter of $\alpha = 0.89$. In the Negative

Binomial model, the parameter indicates an average reduction of 1.07% in collaboration for every 100 km of distance between two universities, *ceteris paribus*. The interpretation of this parameter is not linear, as discussed by Long and Freese (2001, p. 491). For instance, a distance of 1,000 km between two universities reduces the probability of collaboration by 10.27%.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

Global scientific production is characterized by a process of geographical deconcentration, although global cities can be seen as benefiting from international competition (Grossetti et al., 2012). The factor of geographical proximity enhances knowledge flows, particularly when considering the cognitive proximity of research (Abramo et al., 2020). However, as Abramo et al. (2020b) note, this phenomenon varies across national, continental, and transcontinental contexts, especially in the case of Italy. Similarly, Sidone et al. (2016) found evidence of the deconcentration process in Brazilian scientific production but clarified that they did not find evidence suggesting that the impact of geographic distance diminishes over time.

Our results revealed a persistent geographical effect on scientific production (see Table 1). This finding aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the significance of geographical proximity. However, the magnitude of the cognitive parameter underscores its importance. Regarding limitations, the OpenAlex database is relatively new and presents significant potential, as discussed by Priem et al. (2022). Future studies could explore how the interplay between cognitive and geographical proximities has evolved over time, investigating potential moderating effects. For the regression analysis, these studies may need to control for certain variables, such as the ranking of institutions.

Open science practices

All data used in this research are open access. Scripts for data retrieval, processing and analysis are available at the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/insyspo/openalex>.

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Author contributions

Luís Fabiano Farias Borges: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing—original draft. Alysson Mazoni: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing—review & editing.

Competing interests

There are no competing interests.

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References

- Abramo, G., D'Angelo, C. A., & Di Costa, F. (2020a). Does the geographic proximity effect on knowledge spillovers vary across research fields? *Scientometrics*, *123*(2), 1021–1036. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03411-x>
- Abramo, G., D'Angelo, C. A., & Di Costa, F. (2020b). Knowledge spillovers: Does the geographic proximity effect decay over time? A discipline-level analysis, accounting for cognitive proximity, with and without self-citations. *Journal of Informetrics*, *14*(4), 101072. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2020.101072>
- Boschma, R. A. (2005). Proximity and Innovation: A Critical Assessment. *Regional Studies*, *39*(1), 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0034340052000320887>
- Boschma, R., & Frenken, K. (2009). The spatial evolution of innovation networks: a proximity perspective. In R. M. Ron Boschma (Ed.), *The Handbook of Evolutionary Economic Geography* (pp. 120–135). Edward Elgar Publishing Limited.
- Broekel, T. (2015). The Co-evolution of Proximities – A Network Level Study. *Regional Studies*, *49*(6), 921–935. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2014.1001732>
- Cameron, A. C., & Trivedi, P. K. (2013). *Regression Analysis of Count Data* (C. U. Press., Ed.; Second Edi). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139013567>
- Chen, K., Zhang, Y., & Fu, X. (2019). International research collaboration: An emerging domain of innovation studies? *Research Policy*, *48*(1), 149–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.005>
- Gertler, M. S. (2003). Tacit knowledge and the economic geography of context, or the undefinable tacitness of being (there). *Journal of Economic Geography*, *3*(1), 75–99.
- Glaeser, E. L., Kallal, H. D., Scheinkman, J. A., & Schleifer, A. (1992). Growth in Cities. *Journal of Political Economy*, *100*(6), 1126–1152.
- Grossetti, M., Eckert, D., Gingras, Y., Jégou, L., & Larivière, V. (2012). The Geographical Deconcentration of Scientific Activities (1987-2007). *Proceedings of 17th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, *1*(January 2015), 348–356. http://sticonference.org/Proceedings/vol1/Grossetti_Geographical_348.pdf
- Hilbe, J. M. (2011). *Negative binomial regression*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511973420>
- Hoekman, J., Frenken, K., & Tijssen, R. J. W. (2010). Research collaboration at a distance: Changing spatial patterns of scientific collaboration within Europe. *Research Policy*, *39*(5), 662–673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2010.01.012>
- Long, J. S., & Freese, J. (2001). *Regression models for categorical dependent variables using Stata* (T. S. P. College Station, Ed.).
- Nelson, R. R. (1990). Capitalism as an engine of progress. *Research Policy*, *19*(3), 193–214.

Newman, M. E. J. (2001). The structure of scientific collaboration networks. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 98(2), 404–409. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.98.2.404>

Nooteboom, B. (2000). Learning and Innovation in Organizations and Economies. In *Learning and Innovation in Organizations and Economies*. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199241002.001.0001>

Ponds, R., van Oort, F., & Frenken, K. (2007). The geographical and institutional proximity of research collaboration. *Papers in Regional Science: The Journal of the Regional Science Association International*, 86(3), 423–443. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1435-5957.2007.00126.x>

Scherngell, T., & Barber, M. J. (2011). Distinct spatial characteristics of industrial and public research collaborations: Evidence from the fifth EU Framework Programme. *Annals of Regional Science*, 46, 247–266. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00168-009-0334-3>

Scherngell, T., & Hu, Y. (2011). Collaborative Knowledge Production in China: Regional Evidence from a Gravity Model Approach. *Regional Studies*, 45(6), 755–772. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343401003713373>

Sen, A., & Smith, T. E. (1995). *Gravity models of spatial interaction behavior* (Springer, Ed.).

Sidone, O. J. G., Haddad, E. A., & Mena-Chalco, J. P. (2016). Scholarly publication and collaboration in Brazil: The role of geography. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(1), 243–258. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23635>

Storper, M., & Venables, A. J. (2004). Buzz: Face-to-face contact and the urban economy. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 4(4), 351–370. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnlecg/lbh027>

Van Eck, N. J., & Waltman, L. (2024). *An open approach for classifying research publications*. 2024. Retrieved March 19, 2024, from <https://www.leidenmadtrics.nl/articles/an-open-approach-for-classifying-research-publications>